

Deliverable 1.2

Research Data Management Plan

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	In this research data management plan, we provide a description of information concerning the types of data that will be obtained during the course of the project and details relating to how this data will be stored as well as made accessible and shareable both during the project duration and after its completion. Processes for ensuring data security as well as responsible research and innovation aspects are also detailed.
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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reuse of Digital Assets
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
OS	Open Science
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

Research and innovation in the GREAT project will generate new knowledge of the actual and potential impact of games on European society and new understandings of the innovative uses of games to support the social engagement of citizens. Leveraging the central role of games in contemporary culture, it combines academic studies and practical experimentation with novel applications of games. Using collaborative design and citizen science methods, it brings together researchers with expertise in the areas of games, data analytics, and policy in an integrated investigation, articulated by case studies of the use of games in facilitating dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders (policy makers, policy implementers, political parties, campaigning organisations and affected citizens). The context for the research is the climate emergency, and each case study is a research cycle addressing a policy issue and research questions, with multiple pilots and quantitative and qualitative research activities. An important aspect of the method is to place games in an authentic context, so that players are aware that their activities have real-world implications, and to close the loop by including interactions with policy stakeholders. Agile methods are applied to adapt games from existing platforms, for use as research tools: (a) short games deployed at scale in hit mobile games, generating quantitative data and reaching 3 million players, and (b) longer collaborative games based around social dilemmas with small groups, generating in-depth qualitative data.

This document provides a summary of the information concerning the research data that will be collected during the course of the project. It provides as much information as possible at this stage and the data management plan (DMP) is intended to be a living document in which information on data managed in the project can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur. This document will be updated by partner institutions at any time during the project. In particular, for the preparation of the mid-term review, the consortium will address the possible requirement for updating the document and the processes described. Overall, the leading framework for our data management is the GDPR in terms of personal data protection and the FAIR principles will be applied to our collected data for the handling of non-personal data and the data will be made open access following the European Union's Open Science Guidelines. This document outlines the processes of making our project research data accessible and interoperable in order to increase data re-use. The document concludes with the processes of maintaining data security as well as the responsible research and innovation aspects. This document refers to Task 1.3 Open Data Management, Ethics and Responsible Research and Innovation of the Grant Agreement, which covers this plan to ensure openness of research data.

2. Introduction

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of most research projects that collect or handle original data. This DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the GREAT project, following the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020 provided by the European Commission. As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), a DMP should include information on:

- the handling of original data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)

This document provides a first version of the DMP and includes all the available information currently. As stated in the guidelines, the DMP is intended to be a living document in which information on data managed in the project can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the project implementation progresses and when significant changes occur. Therefore, we will implement this deliverable as a document that can be updated by the partner organisations at any time in the course of the project. In preparation for the mid-term review, we will also reflect on the status of the DMP with the consortium and address any possible requirement for updating the document and the processes described in it.

As detailed in the Project Quality Assurance Handbook (D1.1), GREAT is committed to the integrative concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), which clearly goes beyond a pure ethical aspect. The importance of the RRI approach for this project is to align the co-creation process, which is an integral part of most activities, in a reflective way that is both a transparent and interactive process by which societal actors and innovators become mutually responsive to each other. So as to ensure alignment with RRI, the project will develop several activities around a reflective RRI process for all its stakeholders, as summarized in D1.1.

By involving different stakeholders in our project activities, sensitive ethical issues and data may result. All private data and especially sensitive data will be protected, as detailed in D1.1, as consortium partners and members intend to collaborate when collecting, processing and handling data as well as ensuring privacy and security of data is maintained. The consortium will build on the ongoing European guidelines on the management of trust and codes of conduct. All work packages will examine

specifically all ethical and legal aspects related to the data being handled and a responsible Data Protection Officer (DPO) at the DIPF coordinating partner (Viktorija Meinel) will be able to advise and support as necessary concerning any (intricate and complex) details relating to data protection, ethics and privacy, arising from any of the research data or its collection processes.

3. Data Summary

The type of data being handled by this project will increasingly be updated in the live document, as the data managed can be made subsequently available on a finer level of granularity throughout project updates as the project progresses. In the following, we list the main characteristics that describe data as well as the intended project data to be collected, in Table 2 (at the end of this document).

3.1 Type of data

Following the DMP of the GREAT project (EU Grant Agreement, 2022), the following types of data may be collected and documented in our research project:

- **Observational:** data captured through observation of an activity and/or a behavior in real-time (and, therefore, usually irreplaceable). Some observational data collection will require human observation, ethnography, and potentially also instruments, including surveys, interviews, focus groups, to record the information. Observational data may be collected in automated ways, such as with SGI's DIBL or Playmob's Quiz System.
- **Experimental:** data obtained in controlled situations through the active intervention of researchers, who design an activity (called the experiment) to collect data. Such data can be reproduced if needed, but it may be time-consuming and expensive.
- **Simulational:** data generated through reproduction of a real-world system, usually used to determine what would happen in certain conditions.
- **Derived or Compiled:** data derived upon transformation of existing datasets to create new data. Such data can be reproduced if lost, but it is very time-consuming and it could be expensive.
- **Reference or Canonical:** to data used to categorize and/or classify other data. They could be static or changing over time.

- **Event-related:** data collected during events. As they are derived from real-time events, the data is irreplaceable. If they include personal data of participants, just as in the other types of data, GDPR will be applied.

While most of the research data can be assigned to one of these categories, in some cases there could also be an overlap. Some data can belong to more than one category depending on the specificities of the data itself (e.g. event-related data could also be considered observational data under certain conditions).

3.2 Context appropriate data usage standards

As the term 'data' encompasses a broad spectrum of information generated and collected at various stages of the project lifecycle, some of the requirements and guidelines laid out in this document may not apply equally to all pieces of data. This can be because certain processes are inapplicable, or they conflict with how the data is handled or processed. These deviations will be noted explicitly later in this document and would not interfere with the project's legal requirements or ethical standards. Additional, context specific data management details may be added at a later date once we have completed a full cycle from data gathering to publication.

3.3 Reuse of existing data and origin of data

Next to the collection of genuinely new datasets, research work can also rely on existing data and generate new collections out of existing data sources (= derived or compiled data; sometimes also referred to as secondary data). The reuse of existing data sources will thus also be identified as well as the origin of the data to be used in the research process.

3.4 Format of the data and estimated size

Our data can have various formats: text, numeric, multimedia, models, software languages, codes and design, discipline and instrument specific, etc. It is important to describe the format of the data in order to facilitate its accessibility and interoperability. Preference will be given to open and standard formats.

Likewise, data management experts recommend assigning indications about the size of the data collected in a DMP. Similar to the format of the data, size is relevant for future data-sharing and making data accessible. In the course of the project, time information about the size of the managed data should be revised and updated accordingly.

3.5 Aim of the data and the process of data collection

Part of the data description will always be the aim of the data produced and how it is linked to the objectives of the project. Similarly, a short description of the process of the data collection will be applied so as to help to characterize the specific data. A central document serving as a reference index of all the major datasets collected or generated will contain a short description along with a link to its location (on Nextcloud, a Git Repository, Zenodo etc). Further details on the format and collection method will then be available in context with the data at these locations. In Table 2 at the end of this document, we describe the project data in as much detail as we can at this stage. We remain cognizant of all the points outlined above, and we will update this table in case of additional data being handled in any of our research activities.

4. FAIR Data

FAIR data means that the data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. In this section, we elaborate on the measures that the project is taking to generate and handle data according to the FAIR principles, during the and after the project ends.

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Versioning

The datasets produced will follow good research practice by following a set of naming and versioning conventions, which are very useful for collaborative projects. A version control system will be applied to make sure that the data is organised and we can track back among different versions of the datasets. Such a version control system, which is also sometimes referred to as a revision control system, tracks incremental versions (or revisions) of files over time.

Nextcloud is the main data-sharing system running on the DIPF server, which supports a simple, automated version control system for files and documents. Through the use of this version control system, GREAT will minimize the risk of losing information after modifications in collaborative processes, where many consortium members will be working simultaneously with the data. All consortium partners have access to the DIPF Nextcloud.

In addition to the automated versioning via Nextcloud, for its content we may also apply version numbers in the file names themselves (see naming convention below). When dealing with larger amounts of raw data (e.g. when exported from project games), a dedicated git repository will be a more suitable solution, especially when

this data is accompanied by project specific scripting used to process it. Such a repository could be set up on GitLab and will enable better synchronization workflows.

4.1.2 Naming

For the naming of our shareable data, we will use file names that are informative and useful for both humans and machines in order to make the data accessible and findable. Names must be meaningful, on the one hand, in order to make it easy for others to understand what the file contains and how it should be used. On the other hand, the names should use deliberate delimits in order to be machine readable. A common approach is using “_” and “-” to delimit units of metadata in the file names. For this project, we will aim to use “-” to separate words we want to glob together, and “_” to separate different information within a file name. We will not use blank spaces, punctuation, upper-casing of entire words, or special characters (e.g. characters such as \$, @, %, #, &*, (,), !, etc., which may have meanings in programming languages).

As mentioned above the file-naming should also always include a version number to make sure others who want to make use of any dataset know that they are dealing with which version. An example of an appropriate name for a data file is:

GREAT_BusinessModels_Collection_Codes_v1.xml

4.1.3 Metadata and keywords

Once data has been formatted and shared for wider internal or public use, descriptive and substantive (i.e. how the data should be read or interpreted) metadata will be elaborated and described in a readme.txt file complementing each dataset (see Table 1). This detailed documentation should help interested users to clearly understand and reuse the data.

Data in their early stages (such as DIBL or Quiz System raw data exports) prior to processing will go through further internal processing as these contain a subset of the fields below as part of its filename convention, if this is sufficient to identify its point of origin and collection period.

Title	Description
Creator(s)	Main person(s) involved in producing the data.
Title Contributor	Name or title by which the dataset is known. Person(s) or organisation(s) responsible for making contributions to the dataset.
Publisher	Holder of the data (e.g. in archives), or person or institutions who submitted the work.
Data Ownership	Indication of primary data controller (person) and indication of additional data ownership, especially in the case of shared ownership.
Year of publication	The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.
Data created	The date when the resource itself was put together (could be a date range or a single date)
Description	Concise description of the contents of the dataset. Describe the research objective, type of research, method of data collection, type of data and storage location of data.
Subject	Subject, or key phrase describing the resource.
Temporal coverage	The dates to which the data refer (the year or beginning and ending dates).
Spatial coverage	The geographic area to which the data refer (e.g. municipality, town/city, region, country). The geographic coordinates of the area may be included, if desired.
Identifier(s))	Zenodo automatically assigns a DOI to a dataset once the entire deposit procedure has been completed. In some cases, a dataset may be known by one or more (persistent) identifier(s).
Language	The primary language of the resource.

Link to related publication (s)	Include the web addresses or DOIs for any publication, important internal reports or other datasets that are related to your dataset.
Keywords	Keywords that associate with the data resource.

Table 1. Metadata description

As this table shows, each data resource will have a unique identifier, e.g., a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). As we are committed to sharing all our open data on Zenodo, for late-stage data designated for publication, a DOI will be generated and this will serve as our main data identifier. For some data we will apply a more detailed metadata schema, based on the DataCite Metadata Schema: https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.4/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.4.pdf

4.2 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

4.2.1 General rules regarding accessibility

GREAT consortium members support the objective of providing open access to research data as well as research results. Where applicable, project members will use open source licenses for software and non-exclusive licenses for other intellectual property rights such as copyrights, patents or standardization proposals. Also, access to the collected data will be open and free while adhering to privacy and personal data protection. Peer-reviewed scientific publications that result from the project will be provided via open access (“gold” model). We will also submit project publications to Open Research Europe (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>) and the open access publishing platform for scientific articles launched by the European Commission as a free service for H2020 beneficiaries.

Issues related to protecting intellectual property are highly important when citizens and volunteers are involved in the project work. The Consortium Agreement (CA) (signed by all consortium members before the project start) states the details of management of intellectual property rights, including open licenses, between partners are defined. The CA also includes a list of pre-existing know-how (according to the description of work) and knowledge as well as the major principles on exploitation and dissemination issues. The consortium members have already agreed that access rights on the pre-existing know-how needed for carrying out the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

4.2.2 Research data access

The main part of raw and processed data generated by the project will be accessible to all consortium partners, i.e., all data except where there is sensitive data that requires being kept only by the partner having collected the data. As described in the Project Handbook (D1.1), the main workflow for data sharing starts at the work package (WP) level, where each team is responsible for respecting ethical procedures at all times during the data gathering and processing steps. The WP/task team members are also responsible for any data anonymisation or pseudonymization, if applicable. The data accessible to the whole consortium will be stored on the shared Nextcloud server provided by DIPF. Only members of the consortium, after validation by the coordinator (Jane Yau), can access this space. The public data will be accessible via Zenodo and the Open Research Europe platform .

Confidential data and data collected for internal purposes will be stored in the secure facilities of the organization responsible for collecting the data and will be retained for two years after the end of project. Data containing personal identifiable information of individuals will only be shared, when necessary, based on a confidentiality agreement (see Annex I of the Project Quality Assurance Handbook D1.1). A data exchange form, signed by the partners exchanging sensitive data, documents the data exchange between these partners. This form is also provided in D1.1. Details concerning the ownership, transfer and dissemination of project results are defined in section 8 of the Consortium Agreement and shall be followed accordingly. The relevant rules of the Grant Agreement apply accordingly.

4.2.3 Sensitive Social Science Data

In the project, we handle quantitative and qualitative social science data (see Table 2 below), which is often context-sensitive data that includes personal data. GDPR applies for any such personal data, defined as follows:

‘personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person; (Art. 4(1), GDPR)

Thus we will pay careful attention not only to avoid direct identifiers in our data, but also indirect identifiers that could make persons identifiable through aggregation of information. For special categories of personal data, it may even be necessary to provide for certain suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights

and the interests of the data subject. Protection of data subjects according to GDPR rules will take clear precedence over our commitment and intention to contribute as much as possible to open research. If necessary, we may also apply data encryption to make sure sensitive personal data is protected.

There are certain measures that can be taken to allow qualitative social scientific data to be made available and shareable, and we will make use of these measures as much as possible. This includes e.g. clear procedures for informed consent (see our Project Quality Assurance Handbook for details), anonymisation, pseudonymisation, and/or access restrictions. We will eliminate direct and indirect identifiers through one or more of the following:

- Deleting certain information
- Substituting personal identifiers with pseudonyms (more relevant for qualitative data, e.g. interview transcripts)
- Aggregating the information (more relevant for quantitative data, e.g. numeric dataset)

If we allow restricted access to the research data to enable data sharing for scientific purposes, we will follow the principle of “as open as possible - as closed as necessary”. Shared dataset will be published on the Open Research Europe platform. Such restricted access could be granted to a predefined group of users or to certain accounts and under certain conditions. Within the consortium, we also have a data sharing agreement in order to exchange research data within the consortium. Such restricted access would only be granted to researchers external to the consortium with the consent of the research subjects.

In cases where datasets can be made freely available as they do not include any personalised data, we will make them available with the corresponding metadata on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=101094766>).

4.2.4 Making data interoperable

The interoperability of the data mostly depends on the metadata that is provided with the data. Table 1 above described the general metadata that we will provide with each of our datasets. In addition, Zenodo requires metadata for the description of any data shared on the portal. This metadata uses a vocabulary that follows the FAIR data principles and that offers export options to international standard formats, such as Dublin Core or the Datacite Metadata Schema, to make the data interoperable.

To allow inter-disciplinary interoperability we plan to use standard vocabularies for all data types present in your datasets. However, there may be uncommon vocabularies being used that stem from the specific context in which we are operating. These context-specific vocabularies may require provision of some additional explanation with the data, in order to make them interoperable across disciplines.

4.3 Increase data reuse through clarifying licenses

The main users of data produced in the project will be the consortium partners. Following an open and participatory approach towards data sharing and re-use, we also consider participants in our project activities as potential users of the collected data. All data will be classified as open, sensitive or closed, with the access and re-usability depending on the classification. For re-use of the data, the following applies:

- Shared data will be freely available on the Open Research Europe platform, subject to the user acknowledging it through citing the name and creator of the dataset. Permission from the main data creator (main researcher) or contributors is not required.
- Sensitive (or confidential/restricted data) may be made available by the data creator after any identifying information has been removed. Reuse of this anonymised/pseudonymised data may be possible, if cited and if agreed to by the dataset creator and its contributors.
- Closed data are not available for sharing or reuse.

The open data generated in this project will carry the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license so as to permit its reuse. As previously mentioned, all relevant open data will be preserved and archived in Zenodo. As far as we can say at this point, all data and items on Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. There is currently no intention to remove the shared data from the repository at any given time. Zenodo is hosted by CERN which has an experimental programme defined for the next 20+ years, offering long-term accessibility of the data.

5. Allocation of Resources

GREAT is part of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), a pilot action on open access to research data, which requires projects to define and execute a Data Management Plan (i.e., the plan outlined in this document). GREAT's open data management is part of the WP1 - Project Management and Coordination, under the lead of the coordinator partner DIPF. All other consortium partners are committed to contributing to the data management in their roles as WP leaders. As outlined in the

Project Quality Assurance Handbook (D1.1), this DMP will be revised during the course of project activities. As the co-design approach that GREAT is following is a rather dynamic methodology, it is not possible to clearly specify all data sources and collected outcomes at this stage.

The costs for making any of our research data using the FAIR guidelines can be covered by the project budget during the official funding period. According to the Grant Agreement, costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

6. Data Security

Some of the research data from this project will be stored on the collaboration space Nextcloud, which is running on a DIPF server and is fully GDPR compliant. DIPF is running its own IT infrastructure, and it's IT staff maintains it to the highest degree to ensure data security and protection via these measures, among others:

- in-house servers controlled exclusively by DIPF IT staff
- services running in a demilitarized network zone behind a redundant firewall
- resource isolation for services through hardware nodes and/or virtual machines
- regular updates of system and application software
- timely installation of security patches from OSS suppliers
- daily backups, off-site backup on encrypted hard disks, monitoring and logging
- web server hardening
- a password policy for protected data
- consultation and awareness-raising with DIPF staff on data protection issues
- precautions for emergency scenarios
- compliance with GDPR

The Nextcloud collaboration space has a versioning service so that data can also be restored in case of any accidental deletion. Consortium partners may also store the data they generate on their own secure servers, making sure that secure storage is guaranteed. The conditions for transfer of any sensitive data are described above and in the Project Handbook (D1.1).

In other cases, data may initially be created on bespoke infrastructure like SGI's DIBL or Playmob's Event Reporting backends. In this case, it will be stored under similar, but not necessarily identical conditions as listed above.

Under no circumstance will the project collect, store or process private information, etc. without the explicit and written permission of the respective persons. GREAT will comply fully with data protection provisions as set out in the currently applicable Data Protection Directive EC 95/46, the General Data Protection Regulation EU/2016/679 (GDPR) and the e-Privacy Directive EC 2002/58 (confidentiality of information, treatment of traffic data, spam and cookies).

7. Responsible Research and Innovation Aspects

7.1 Research must respect ethical standards and fundamental rights to respond to societal challenges

During the lifetime of the project, GREAT will continuously follow an approach that ensures an appropriate level of ethical sensitivity, meaning that any changes and implementations will be viewed from an ethical perspective and (where needed) actions taken accordingly. The academic consortium partners have internal ethical boards and will seek their approval for any data sensitive activities. The Project Quality Assurance Handbook (D1.1) describes in detail the ethical standards we apply for our research, which are aligned with our principles of RRI.

7.2 Gender equality and gender diversity

Our project fully supports the European Union policy on equal opportunities between women, men and gender-diverse persons. To this end, participation of all genders will be continually encouraged and supported. Project staff of all consortium members are composed according to the principle of equal opportunity and all member organisations strongly enforce an equal opportunity policy in their human resources selection processes. In addition, we are aware of inherent gender biases that can be present and will follow a gender-sensitive methodology, following gender-sensitive principles. Any dataset openly shared will as far as possible be controlled for bias, as well as for research ethics and integrity.

Of specific importance for the project is the aspect of learning and knowledge sharing. For example, within the specific (1) citizens and game players, (2) academia (games researchers, social scientists, technologists), (3) game publishers and providers, games developers, (4) policy makers, policy implementers, environmental policy stakeholders, 5) political parties and campaigning organisations. It is critical that we transfer our

findings into useful knowledge resources for the target communities, e.g., via press releases, research and conference publications, industry and climate crisis conferences and social media. Therefore, the project has excellent potential for the enhancement of current education processes to better equip future makers, entrepreneurs and society as a whole with the necessary competences to participate in collective and responsible processes.

8. Summary and outlook

This document, together with the Project Quality Assurance Handbook (D1.1), describes the main aspects of how this project will practice open research and how the consortium will handle the collected research data. The project team is fully committed to open science and openness as defaults, whilst simultaneously ensuring the privacy and data security of personal data derived from the research participants is of the highest priority. Templates and procedures for data collection, including for ethical compliance, are in place and will be utilised by the project team. As research data management is a continuous process and we can currently not foresee all eventualities that may arise through following an open co-design methodology, we will reflect on and update this DMP in the course of the project.

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Work package & activity of data collection	Short data description & aim of the data	Type & format of data (incl. any reuse)
<p><i>WP2 (Intervention Design)</i></p>	<p>The aim of the data collection is to support and document collaborative design of interventions.</p> <p>Data will be generated in the course of design activities. Depending on the activity design, this may include transcripts of conversations, shared documents and artifacts, video recordings and field notes. Questionnaires may be used to collect design ideas and provide feedback. Exports from online collaborative platforms</p>	<p><i>Qualitative data</i> <i>Observational data</i> <i>Design data</i> Audio (ogg) Video (MP4) Text (ODF) Images (jpg) Vector graphics (SVG) <i>No reuse is planned</i></p>
<p><i>WP3 (Technical Development and Repurposing of Games)</i></p>	<p>DIBL (SGI): The long dilemma games aim to inform us the preferences and attitudes of citizens relating to a particular Climate theme.</p> <p>Quiz System (Playmob): Anonymised data is logged as 'User Actions' performed during Playmob quiz sessions, which include answers given to quiz questions, as well as other milestones such as external links clicked. This data will be provided to other partners for further data analysis.</p> <p>It will come either as raw session data or aggregated by distributions and/or date.</p> <p>Quiz configuration and asset data is also provided, in order to match the question/answer indexes to the actual text copy shown to the player in the quiz.</p>	<p>Observational <i>Event-related (anonymous)</i></p> <p>.csv .xls .json</p> <p><i>The data in the games are exported from PlayMob and SGI proprietary databases.</i></p>
<p><i>WP4 (Case Studies and Research Outputs)</i></p>	<p>Data will be generated in the course of research activities. Depending on the research activity design, this may include transcripts of conversations, shared documents and artifacts, video recordings and field notes. Questionnaires may be used to collect design</p>	<p><i>Qualitative and Quantitative data observational data</i> Audio (ogg) Video (MP4)</p>

	ideas and provide feedback. Exports from online collaborative platforms	Text (ODF) Images (jpg) Vector graphics (SVG) .CSV, .XIS, .json
<i>WP5 (Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications)</i>	<p>Data will be generated in the course of research activities. This may include transcripts of interviews, workshops and focus groups, conversations, shared documents and artifacts, video and audio recordings and field notes.</p> <p>Questionnaires may be used to collect opinions, experiences, or feedback. Exports from online collaborative platforms may be used as well.</p> <p>Use of existing research data where/when available relevant to research activity yet to be determined and in baseline literature review & studies.</p>	<p>Qualitative and Quantitative data observational data Event-related data Audio (ogg, mp4, mp3), Video (MP4) Text (ODF, docx) Images (jpg, png, heic), Vector graphics (SVG), .CSV, .XIS Extracts from Miro Board and other collaboration tools (PDF, JPEG), audio recordings</p>
<i>WP6 (Engagement, Dissemination, and Sustainability)</i>	<p>Data collected, based on specs listed under WP3 (Technical Development and Repurposing of Games)</p> <p>Stakeholder contact details - existing and new (generated from events, social media and the website)</p>	<p>Quantitative data, event driven data (engagement rate stats) Contact details Existing data will include the raw data from the People’s Climate Vote and Green Game Jam 2021 and 2022 study Existing stakeholder details</p>

Table 2. Data description of the GREAT project

